

Second Order Cross-Phenomenological Coefficient (Electro-Osmosis of Water)

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A second order cross-phenomenological coefficient has been evaluated, qualitatively, from available experimental data on the steady state electro-osmotic pressure developed for various values of applied potential gradient through a water/pyrex sinter system. The evaluation has been made by graphical analysis of the data for the range in which electro-osmotic permeability has been found to be linearly related to the applied voltage. Statistical considerations, show that the second order cross-phenomenological coefficient is of the order of $10^{-4} \text{ cm}^5 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ volt}^{-1} \text{ dyne}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{K}^2$. The results thus obtained are in conformity with the results reported earlier. Further, fairly good agreement between the values obtained from the intercepts in the graphical analysis and those obtained from direct experimental results in solvodynamic and electro-osmotic permeabilities through the system at the same temperature also suggests, on qualitative basis atleast, that the values of the second order coefficient, thus evaluated, are fairly dependable.

Phenomenological laws are of great importance in thermodynamics of irreversible processes^{1,2}. They are used as axioms to describe the transport processes near equilibrium when two or more forces are involved³⁻⁵. Using Taylor's expansion, the expression for flows around equilibrium, if any flow J_i is a function of the forces X_1, X_2, \dots , is given by⁶⁻⁸

$$J_i = \sum_j L_{ij} X_j + \frac{1}{2} \sum_j \sum_k L_{ijk} X_j X_k + \dots \quad \dots (1)$$

Where L_{ij} and L_{ijk} are the derivatives of various orders of J given⁹ by

$$L_{ij} = (\partial J_i / \partial X_j)_{eq}, \quad L_{ijk} = (\partial^2 J_i / \partial X_j \partial X_k)_{eq} \quad \dots (2)$$

They are known as phenomenological coefficients or proportionality constants. The subscript 'eq' denotes the values of the derivatives at equilibrium.

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In electro-osmosis, the phenomenological relation between the rate of transport of matter, J , pressure difference, ΔP , and potential difference, $\Delta\phi$, is given by the expression^{4, 10, 11}

$$J = L_{11}(\Delta P/T) + L_{12}(\Delta\phi/T) + L_{111}(\Delta P/T)^2 + L_{112}(\Delta P/T)(\Delta\phi/T) + L_{122}(\Delta\phi/T)^2 + \dots \quad (3)$$

where L_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2$) and L_{ijk} ($i, j, k = 1, 2$) are respectively the first order and the second order phenomenological coefficients. When $i \neq j$ and/or K the coefficients are known as cross-phenomenological coefficients. Since Poiseuille's law has much greater range of validity L_{111} would be zero³ for a fairly high value of ΔP . The rate of electro-osmotic permeation, $(J)_{\Delta P=0}$, is given by

$$(J)_{\Delta P=0} = L_{12}(\Delta\phi/T) + L_{122}(\Delta\phi/T)^2 + \dots \quad (4)$$

In the linear range equation (4) reduces to

$$(J)_{\Delta P=0} = L_{12}(\Delta\phi/T) \quad (5)$$

The difficulty encountered in the measurements of electro-osmotic permeability and steady state electro-osmotic pressure developed, at high voltages, for water/pyrex sinter system has already been pointed out⁴. Precise measurements at higher voltages with the system could not be made which could yield direct information about the second order cross-phenomenological coefficient in this case. Nevertheless, the available data for the system can be used to obtain qualitative information about the cross-phenomenological coefficient. Experimental results³ for the electro-osmosis of deionized water through sintered pyrex disc show that while the electro-osmotic permeation, $(J)_{\Delta P=0}$, is linearly related to the applied potential difference, $\Delta\phi$, up to 80 volts, the steady state values of the electro-osmotic pressure, $(\Delta P)_{J=0}$, developed become non-linear with the applied potential difference when the value of $\Delta\phi$ exceeds 60 volts only. The logical consequence which follows from these observations of the system is that in electro-osmosis, while the linear relationship between the transport of matter and the applied potential gradient is obeyed by the system for $\Delta\phi$ up to 80 volts when $\Delta P = 0$, it seems to be most certainly disturbed at $\Delta\phi = 60$ volts and above when $\Delta P \neq 0$. Beyond 60 volts there is a definite departure from the linearity when $\Delta\phi$ and ΔP both operate simultaneously through the system. Evidently then the second order term in the R.H.S. of eq. (4) or the 5th term in the R.H.S. of eq. (3) remains inoperative at least up to $\Delta\phi = 80$ volts with the system. Validity of Poiseuille's equation for a fairly high values of ΔP also suggests that the contribution of the third term in the R.H.S. of eq. (3) is also zero for the little value of $(\Delta P)_{J=0}$ developed in the range of $\Delta\phi$ up to 80 volts. Eq. (3) for this range of applied potential difference may be written as

$$J = L_{11}(\Delta P/T) + L_{12}(\Delta\phi/T) + L_{112}(\Delta P/T)(\Delta\phi/T) \quad (6)$$

In the steady state $J = 0$ and by simple transformation of eq. (6) we get

$$(\Delta P)_{J=0} = (-L_{12}/L_{11})\Delta\phi + (-L_{112}/L_{11})(\Delta P/T)\Delta\phi \quad (7)$$

Eq. (7) explains the non-linear character of the variation of the electro-osmotic pressure with the applied voltage. The non-linear character becomes observable when $\Delta\phi$ exceeds 60 volts.

10. K. M. Jha, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 987.

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At this stage the second order cross-phenomenological coefficient, L_{112} , becomes operative and meaningful with the applied voltage and the developed electro-osmotic pressure, $(\Delta P)_{J=0}$.

Eq. (7) may conveniently be written as

$$(\Delta\phi/\Delta P)_{J=0} = (-L_{11}/L_{12}) + (-L_{112}/L_{12}) \cdot (\Delta\phi/T) \quad \dots (8)$$

and

$$(\Delta P/\Delta\phi)_{J=0} = (-L_{12}/L_{11}) + (-L_{112}/L_{11}) \cdot (\Delta P/T) \quad \dots (9)$$

which may comfortably be analyzed graphically with the available experimental data, for getting the information about the order and magnitude of L_{112} . The object of this communication is to report such an attempt.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

$(\Delta\phi/\Delta P)_{J=0}$, at constant temperature has been plotted against $\Delta\phi$ in figure (1). Recent experimental data on electro-osmosis of water³ have been used for the purpose. The points are a little scattered. They, however, satisfy the linearity test¹². The correlation coefficient¹³ for the data is found to be 0.74. On statistical considerations¹⁴⁻¹⁶, therefore, we may safely conclude that the data are linearly related, with less than 3% risk of making an error. The

Fig. 1

slope gives the value of $L_{112}/L_{12}T$ and the intercept is equal to (L_{11}/L_{12}) . These were evaluated by the method of least squares¹⁷. The magnitude and the order of the slope is found to

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be $6.34 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ dyne}^{-1}$ from which the values of L_{112}/T^2 and L_{112} obtained are $4.44 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^5 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ volt}^{-1} \text{ dyne}^{-1}$ and $4.10 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^5 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ volt}^{-1} \text{ dyne}^{-1} \text{ OK}^2$ respectively. These values are in fair agreement with our previous observations⁴. The value of the intercept is found to be $2.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ volt dyne}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ as against $(2.28 \pm 0.13) \times 10^{-3} \text{ volt dyne}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$, obtained as the ratio of the experimentally observed values of the specific rate of solvodynamic permeation³ ($L_{11} = 1.59 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^5 \text{ dyne}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) to that of the specific rate of electro-osmotic permeation³ ($L_{12} = \{7.0 \pm 0.4\} \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ volt}^{-1}$ for $\Delta\phi$ up to 80 volts) through the system at the same temperature (35°). The agreement between the two values is quite good.

Fig. 4

$(\Delta P/\Delta\phi)_{j=0}$ may, similarly, be plotted against $(\Delta P)_{j=0}$. This has been done in figure (2). The correlation factor in this case is found to be 0.75 which confirms the linear relation¹³ between the variables. On similar considerations, as we discussed above, the values of the slope, giving $(L_{112}/L_{11}T)$, and the intercept, giving (L_{12}/L_{11}) , are found to be $16.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ volt}^{-1}$ and $4.84 \times 10^2 \text{ dyne cm}^{-2} \text{ volt}^{-1}$ respectively. The value of the intercept obtained from the experimental values of L_{12} and L_{11} in this case is $4.40 \times 10^2 \text{ dyne cm}^{-2} \text{ volt}^{-1}$. The agreement between the two values is again fair and satisfactory. The values of L_{112}/T^2 and L_{112} as obtained from the slope are $2.54 \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^5 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ dyne}^{-1} \text{ volt}^{-1}$ and $2.40 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^5 \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ volt}^{-1} \text{ dyne}^{-1} \text{ OK}^2$ respectively which agrees well with the values reported earlier⁴. It may be noted that due to very small order and magnitude of L_{112} , its contribution could hardly be noticed for the system working at lower voltage (50 volt) for which linear phenomenological equation has been found to hold good³. In acetone/pyrex sinter system, however, the system could be subjected to a potential difference of 450 volts (the maximum range for which studies could be made⁴) without any risk of getting the specific conductivity of the medium altered. It has thus been possible with this system to evaluate the contribution of L_{112} directly.